

Pollutions Lead To Increase In Diseases

Nabla.T

Mcom Student Emea Collage Of Arts And Science

Email-Nabualfath0@gmail.com.

Abstract

Environmental pollution is a major concern in developing countries of the world, especially in Nigeria. This Issue of pollution is a terrible negative vibe or influence on all the living things and the environment. Pollution Of the environment via air, land and water by human activities is detrimental to the existence of all living things Within the society which is not an acceptable development at all. Air pollution is caused by several factors such As emission from motor vehicles, industrial activities, volcanic eruption, emitting poisonous, forest fire, Deforestation, bush burning and cosmic clouds of dusts. Soil pollution is also caused by factors such as oil Spillage, human erosion and contamination by hazardous substances. Water pollution is caused by oil discharge From vessels, dumping from ships and aircrafts, wastes disposal from land, oil spillage, organic sources and Other means of polluting the environment. Pollution is a vital environmental disaster due to the fact that some Known and unknown diseases are discovered and might be difficult to subdue. In this article environmental Pollution will be discussed under three classes of pollution that is the water, the soil, and the air land their impact On human health; also needed measures to reduce pollution in Nigeria as a case study.

Keywords: Air; Land; Water Pollution; Diseases; Environment; Human Health; Pollution.

Introduction

Pollution is the introduction of harmful materials into the environment. These harmful materials are called pollutants. Pollutants can be natural, such as volcanic ash. They can also be created by human activity, such as trash or runoff produced by factories. Pollutants damage the quality of air, water, and land.

There is different pollution in the world. The day today the pollutions will increase in several cities the example is Air pollutants in New Delhi. But most important point noted that all the pollutions are made the human beings. Pollution is linked to three main human activities: fossil-fuel combustion, primarily by industry and transport; the application of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture; and the growing use and complexity of chemicals.

Purpose/Aim:

The main aim of this study is to pollutants will lead to increase the diseases and causes of increasing the decrease, how to prevent the pollutions.

Theoretical Review

Several Pollutions Affecting Diseases

Air Pollutants:

Air pollution is the contamination of air due to the presence of substances in the atmosphere that are harmful to the health of humans and other living beings, or cause damage to the climate or to materials.

Main causes of this pollution is Vehicle emissions, fuel oils and natural gas to heat homes, by-products of manufacturing and power generation, particularly coal-fueled power plants, and fumes from chemical production are the primary sources of human-made air pollution.

Effects of air pollutions Long-term health effects from air pollution Long-term health effects from air pollution include heart disease, lung cancer, and respiratory diseases such as emphysema. Air pollution can also cause long-term damage to people's nerves, brain, kidneys, liver, and other organs. Some scientists suspect air pollutants cause birth defects.

Water Pollutions:

Water pollution is the contamination of water sources by substances which make the water unusable for doing activities. Pollutants include chemicals, trash, bacteria, and parasites.

Causes of the water pollution are caused by pathogenic microbes that can be directly spread through contaminated water. Most waterborne diseases cause diarrheal illness

Noise Pollutions

The propagation of noise with ranging impacts on the activity of human or animal life, most of them are harmful to a degree. The source of outdoor noise worldwide is mainly caused by machines, transport, and propagation systems.

It's badly affect the stress related illnesses, high blood pressure, speech interference, hearing loss, sleep disruption, and lost productivity.

Light Pollutions

Light pollution is the presence of anthropogenic artificial light in otherwise dark conditions. Light pollution is a side-effect of industrial civilization. Its sources include building exterior and interior lighting, advertising, outdoor area lighting (such as car parks), offices, factories, streetlights, and illuminated sporting venues.

It effects disrupts the natural patterns of wildlife, contributes to the increase in carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere, disrupts human sleep, and obscures the stars in the night sky.

Litter Pollution

Litter consists of waste products that have been discarded incorrectly, without consent, at an unsuitable location. Litter can also be

used as a verb; to litter means to drop and leave objects, often man-made, such as aluminum cans, paper cups, food wrappers, cardboard boxes or plastic bottles. Litter can be hazardous to health. Debris falling from vehicles is an increasing cause of automobile accidents.[23] Discarded dangerous goods, chemicals, tires, sharps waste and pathogens resulting from litter can cause accidental harm to humans

Plastic Pollution

It s the accumulation of plastic objects and particles (e.g. plastic bottles, bags and microbeads) in the Earth's environment that adversely affects humans, wildlife and their habitat. Plastic pollution increased now a days .Throw plastic carry bags in surroundings and road sides. Its not dilute in soil.

It will affect to increase the cancers nervous system, reproductive and developmental problems, cancer, leukemia, and genetic impacts like low birth weight.

Prevention From Pollutions

Pollution prevention protects the environment by conserving and protecting natural resources while strengthening economic growth through more efficient production in industry and less need for households, businesses and communities to handle waste .To reduce the air pollutions ,Conserve energy – at home, at work, everywhere. Look for the ENERGY STAR label when buying home or office equipment. Carpool, use public transportation, bike, or walk whenever possible.

To prevent from water pollutions to Pick up litter and throw it away in a garbage can.Blow or sweep fertilizer back onto the

grass if it gets onto paved areas. Don't put fertilizer on the grass right before it rains. The chemicals will wash into storm drains and waterways.

To protect the human beings and surrounding from noise pollutions toTurn off Appliances at Home and offices. Shut the Door when using noisy Machines. Use Earplugs. Lower the volume. Stay away from Noisy area. Follow the Limits of Noise level. Control Noise level near sensitive areas. Go Green by planning that the Door when using noisy Machines. Use Earplugs. Lower the volume. Stay away from Noisy area. Follow the Limits of Noise level. ... Control Noise

level near sensitive areas. Go Green by planning trees.

Littering is an environmental issue and requires great attention. However, people are not concerned about the environment. Put your rubbish in a bin. Take your rubbish with you if no bin is available. Keep a bag in your car to collect rubbish. Put your cigarette butt in a butt bin, or an ordinary litter bin when extinguished. Keep a container in your car to collect cigarette butts.

The equivalent of one garbage truck of plastic enters into our seas every minute, every day, all year long. The flow of plastics into our environment has reached crisis proportions, and the evidence is most clearly on display in our oceans. Wean yourself off disposable plastics. Stop buying water. Boycott microbeads. Cook more. Purchase items secondhand. Recycle. Support a bag tax of ban. Buy in bulk.

Graph Rate Of Increasing Pollutions

Conclusion

The protection of man and the environment from harmful effect resulting from all substances introduced into the Atmosphere, water or soil requires the formulation of a comprehensive and interdisciplinary Concept to Comprise general objectives and principles of protective action.

These principles would of course include the instrumentality of law in protecting the environment. There is Therefore the need to increase monitoring of the effects of existing rules on pollution, with the aim of seeing What deficiencies that might be available in any existing rules and laws, and whether further international Conventions relating to the eradication of pollution are to be ratified and domesticated into any law in Developing countries especially in Nigeria law..

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